

Effects of Sodium Azide on Agro-Morphological Traits of Four Varieties of Groundnut (*Arachis Hypogea*)

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Abstract

The seeds of four varieties of groundnut-ROSDOM 204, ROSDOM 306, WAPAN 1 and AGRIC 2 were treated with sodium azide at the concentrations of 0, 1, 2, 4, 10 and 12 millimoles (mM), in the laboratory, Kwara University, Wukari, Taraba State with the aim of determining the effective concentration capable of inducing desirable mutants. Highly significant difference ($p < 0.01$) was observed for percentage germination, height at maturity and weight of 1000 grains. Significant difference ($p < 0.05$) was observed for number of pods per plant, days to first flowering and length of pods. However, the interaction between concentration and variety revealed no significant difference for all traits studied except for percentage germination. The variety Rosdom 204 was observed to be most tolerant to sodium azide treatment. Similarly, 4mM was the most effective concentration for inducing desirable mutants such as weight of 1000 grains and number of pods per plant. Furthermore, there was a highly significant correlation between seedling height and height at maturity. Percentage germination was highly correlated with seedling survival, number of pods per plant and was significantly correlated ($p < 0.05$) for all other traits except percentage germination, length of pods, days to flowering, plant height at maturity and leaf area which showed no significance. In view of the results obtained from this research, low concentration (4mM) of sodium azide can be exploited and utilized for breeding of groundnut for good quality and high yield.

Key words: Groundnut, mutagenesis, concentration, agro-morphology

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Introduction

Groundnut (*Arachis hypogea*), a legume which belongs to the family Fabaceae, is the 13th most important food crop in the world [1], the fourth most important source of oil [2], and the third most important source of protein [3]. Peanut is widely produced in tropical and subtropical regions of the world. World annual production is about 46 million tonnes per year China accounting for 37% of the world production. Africa accounts for 25%, out of which Nigeria produces 3 million tonnes.

Groundnut also known as peanut or goober [4] has a wide range of uses which includes using it for making margarine candy, salted groundnut, oils and soap. It has also been reported that the press cake containing 40-50% protein is used mainly as a high protein livestock feed and as fertilizer [2]. Peanuts can be used like other legumes and grains to make a lactose-free, milk-like beverage, peanut milk, which is promoted in Africa as a way to reduce malnutrition among children. The dry pericarp of the mature pod is used for fuel, while the foliage is used as silage and forage. Additionally, the recent thrust on bio-energy has also brought about possibilities of testing peanut as a bio-diesel crop because groundnut produces more oil per hectare than any other food crop [2]. Against this background, there is high demand on groundnut, hence the need for increased production of this all important crop. This requires great variability.

The sources of plant breeding depend on the presence of genetic variability for desirable traits in crop plants. The main source of this variability is natural mutation, which cannot adequately meet the demands of plant breeders. This is even more so with breeding objectives becoming more complex and demanding. Hybridization has created additional variability with combination of desirable characters. However, breeders need even greater variability against the backdrop of ever increasing demand by farmers for improved varieties [5]. The use of mutagens to create variability is one of the conventional ways of crop improvement [6]. Diethylsulphate was used to create variability at the concentrations of 0.1, 0.3 and 0.5% [7] It is in view of this that the present study intends to investigate the effects of sodium azide on four varieties of groundnut (*Arachis hypogea*).

Materials and Methods

Seeds of three varieties of groundnut (Rosdom 204, Rosdom 306 and Agric 2) obtained from the Institute for Agricultural Research (IAR), Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, and a local variety (Wapan 1) were pre-soaked in phosphate buffer, then introduced into sodium azide at the concentrations of 0, 1, 2, 4, 10 and 12 millimoles respectively for four hours. The seeds were thoroughly washed in running tap water to remove excess mutagen and sown at the experimental site.

Experimental Layout and Seed Planting

The seeds were then sown at the permanent site of Kwararafa university, Wukari using the principle of randomization. There were twenty four plots comprising of six ridges each. Inter- and intra-row spacing was 75cm and 40cm respectively. Each ridge was 8metres long. Weeding of the field was done manually four weeks after planting. Each treatment was replicated thrice and the design followed a randomized complete block design.

Data collection

Germination Count and Percentage: The total number of seeds that emerged per plot was recorded 15 days after planting and the percentage calculated using the formula:

$$\% \text{ Germination} = \frac{\text{No of germinated seeds}}{\text{Total treated seeds}} \times 100$$

Weight of 1000 Grains: The grains of groundnut were threshed and weight was taken with an electric weighing balance in grams.

Height of Plant at Maturity: The height of plant at maturity was taken in cm by measuring the whole plant in cm from the ground level to the highest point of the topmost leaf..

Leaf Area at maturity: Leaf area for matured leaves was calculated using graph sheet.

Number of pods per plant: This was counted manually

Days to flowering: This was noted as the plants flowered

Length of pod: This was measured using a metre rule

Data Analysis:

Statistical analysis was carried out using the SAS 9.0 Package. The data collected were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA). Significance in the treatments was further analyzed using New Duncan's Multiple Range Test (NDMRT) to separate and compare individual means of the varieties.

Results

The results of the study (Table 1) indicated a significant difference among the treated peanut seeds for germination percent, height at maturity, weight of 1000 grains, days to flowering, length of pod and leaf area. A non-significant difference was observed for all other traits. In terms of the response of the varieties to the mutagenic treatment, there was a highly significant difference for germination and weight of 1000 grains. Other traits were significant except for days to flowering. Similarly, the interaction between the varieties and treatment did not reveal any significant difference except for the percentage of seeds that germinated (Table 1)

Table 1: Mean square estimate of agro-morphological traits of groundnut

Source of Variation	DF	Gm %	DTF No.	WT g	HT cm	LP cm	NPP No.	Area cm ²
Replication	24	502.31	15.43*	15834.36	1078.86	4.62	74.85	217.34
Variation	3	166.68**	15.00ns	36619.78*	68.67*	0.2*	63.83*	32.64*
Concentration	15	10.46*	14.27ns	872.45ns	9.56ns	0.05ns	3.36ns	22.70*
Error	14	8.82	15.07	3004.10	13.00	0.1	6.57	4.90

** : Highly significant ($p \leq 0.01$)

* - Significant ($p \leq 0.05$)

Ns - Non significant

Additionally, the results revealed variation in the effectiveness of the concentrations of sodium azide for these traits. Among the treated materials, the highest effect on germination was produced by 4 millimoles. This trend was also observed in height of the plants at maturity and weight of 1000 grains compared with their respective controls (Table 2).

Table 2: Mean performance of four varieties of groundnut treated with sodium azide

Concentration	Gm (%)	DTF (No)	WT (g)	HT (cm)	LP (cm)	NPP (no)	Area (cm ²)
0	95.67 ^a	15.43a	79.96b	24.38ab	1.77b	6.00b	13.91a
1	75.86 ^c	15.00b	77.91b	24.68ab	1.92a	6.83ab	10.91b
2	75.33 ^c	16.00a	79.57b	27.08b	1.81b	5.83b	11.30b
4	90.17 ^b	14.29	109.40a	29.40a	1.77b	7.67a	11.11b
10	75.88 ^{bc}	15.29a	80.16b	26.18b	1.49c	6.00b	10.18b
12	90.67 ^b	14.43ab	55.63c	23.53ab	1.72b	6.33b	10.58b

Means with the same letter are not significant

Key

Gm: Germination percent; **DTF:** Days to flowering; **WT:** Weight of 1000 grains; **HT:** Height of plant maturity; **LP:** Length of pod; **NPP:** number of pods per plant

The mean performance of the four varieties of groundnut also revealed that Rosdom 204 showed the greatest response to the mutagenic treatment for all the traits studied except for days to flowering, length of pod and leaf area for which variety wapan 1 performed better than the other varieties. Rosdom 306 and Agric 2 performed better for leaf area (Table 3).

Table 3: Mean performance of four varieties of groundnut treated with sodium azide

Variety	Gm (%)	DTF (No)	WT (g)	HT (cm)	LP (cm)	NPP (no)	Area (cm ²)
Rosdom 204	95.42 ^a	14.33 ^c	159.70 ^a	29.14 ^a	1.63 ^a	9.50 ^a	9.87 ^b
Rosdom 306	45.38 ^b	16.00 ^b	20.37 ^d	25.56 ^{ab}	1.64 ^a	3.57 ^c	13.14 ^a
Wapan 1	95.00 ^a	16.33 ^a	43.37 ^c	23.75 ^b	1.80 ^a	4.83 ^{bc}	10.50 ^b
Agric 2	95.50 ^a	14.17 ^c	66.08 ^b	23.88 ^b	1.91 ^a	6.83 ^b	13.61 ^a

Means with the same letter are non-significant

Gm: Germination percent; **DTF:** Days to flowering; **WT:** Weight of 1000 grains; **HT:** Height of plant maturity; **LP:** Length of pod; **NPP:** number of pods per plant

Furthermore, Table 4 reveals the mean values of the performance of the groundnut varieties in relation to the mutagenic treatment. The concentration, 4mM gave the highest percentage of seeds that germinated (100%), height at maturity (34cm), number of pods per plant (11) and weight of 1000 grains (206) in all varieties except Agric 2 (Table 4),

Table 4: Mean performance of the effects of sodium azide on four varieties of groundnut

Variety	Concentration	Gm (%)	DTF (No)	WT (g)	HT (cm)	LP (cm)	NPP (no)	Area (cm ²)
Rosdom204	0	95.00	14.33	139.62	27.40	18.80	8.50	8.30
	1	95.00	16.00	157.72	29.65	14.80	10.00	11.15
	2	90.00	16.33	182.46	30.00	17.30	10.00	10.40
	4	100.00	14.17	206.09	34.00	16.30	11.50	9.45
	10	95.00	15.00	184.62	30.55	14.80	10.50	10.45
	12	100.00	15.50	87.72	23.25	16.10	6.50	9.50
	Mean		95.83	15.22	159.71	29.14	16.35	9.50
S.E		2.10	2.00	10.75	2.55	0.23	1.81	1.56
Rosdom306	0	100.00	17.00	127.50	20.80	14.60	3.00	14.80
	1	40.00	15.00	126.56	22.00	19.30	5.00	19.30
	2	50.00	13.00	120.67	32.00	15.00	1.00	15.00
	4	55.00	15.00	113.41	27.70	16.00	4.00	16.00
	10	35.00	13.50	128.48	27.65	14.50	2.50	14.50
	12	65.00	15.50	126.48	24.70	20.00	7.00	20.00
	Mean		57.50	16.00	127.50	20.80	14.60	3.57
S.E		2.30	1.89	1.53	2.00	1.69	1.37	2.30
Wapan 1	0	95.00	14.00	148.67	23.35	11.15	4.50	31.15
	1	90.00	15.00	39.46	23.00	9.95	5.00	29.95
	2	90.00	13.00	132.19	22.60	11.80	3.50	31.80
	4	95.00	15.50	172.05	28.00	11.30	6.00	31.30
	10	92.50	15.00	138.27	22.05	9.60	5.00	29.25
	12	95.00	14.50	128.67	23.50	9.25	5.00	29.25
	Mean		92.83	15.30	143.34	23.75	10.50	4.83
S.E		2.3	1.53	2.55	1.56	1.81	3.62	3.83
Agric 2	0	100.00	14.00	175.67	24.00	11.90	7.00	14.30
	1	100.00	13.00	146.57	23.50	12.16	6.00	14.30
	2	90.00	15.00	145.57	25.30	11.86	7.00	14.40
	4	92.50	15.00	188.55	24.70	12.16	8.00	12.20
	10	100.00	14.00	169.57	22.80	11.63	6.00	10.10
	12	100.00	12.00	170.55	23.00	11.76	7.00	16.40
	Mean		97.08	14.17	166.08	23.88	11.91	6.83
S.E		2.97	1.65	10.64	3.60	0.31	2.56	2.21

Discussion

The results from this study indicated a highly significant variation among the treated materials. This suggests that the mutagenic treatment was effective. The effectiveness of chemical mutagens was demonstrated in urdbean [8]. A similar result was reported in potato [9] where, different concentrations of diethyl sulphate was used to create variability. In this study different concentrations of sodium azide were observed to have significant effect on different agronomic traits of sorghum. Generally, the results revealed that moderate concentration of the mutagen was most effective in bringing about greater response from the research materials studied. Most of the traits increased as the concentration of sodium azide increased as opposed to earlier reports of [10], [11] and [12] who worked on sorghum. In another report, less number of the treated groundnut germinated compared to the control Mayur et al. [13]. They stated that high doses decreased germination percent. The plant height at maturity was found to be highest (34cm) in Rosdom 204 at the concentration of 4mM, and 32cm at 2mM in Rosdom 306 indicating that low and moderate doses of this mutagen leads to increase in height. The results of the present study

revealed however that in some instances higher concentrations gave higher values. For instance, germination percent was (100 %) at the concentration of 12 millimoles in both varieties Rosdom 204 and Agric 2. This may be due to difference in the genetic composition of the genotypes. According to [14] who worked on jute, certain lines with good agronomic characteristics are stable at this concentration. Number of pods was observed to be higher than the control in Rosdom 204 at all concentrations except 12 millimoles (Table 4). This suggests that this variety could be most adapted for better yield of this crop than the others. A similar varietal variation has been reported in *solanum tuberosum* [7]. However, [15] had a contrary view as they reported that growth parameters such as plant height, number of days to flowering, and number of seeds per first fruit decreased considerably when compared with the wild type which, according to them may be as a result of the biological damage to the embryo. This view is also shared by [16], [17] and [18].

The results also revealed that the treated materials developed flowers faster than their respective control. This may be due to the dysfunctional effect of the mutagen at this level thereby inducing flower initiation comparatively earlier than their control. This result is in consonance with the works of [7] and [19] that reported a decrease in the number of days to 50% physiological maturity among their groundnut varieties in the M_1 than in the M_2 . Similarly, [20] reported that there was decrease in the number of days to first flowering in the treated groundnut materials compared with the control (33 and 36 days respectively). Suggesting that at low concentration variability can be created in this plant

Conclusion

Based on the results stated above, it can be concluded that the concentration capable of inducing beneficial mutants such as grain weight, length and number of pods in these varieties of groundnut *Arachis hypogea* with minimal level of damage is 4 millimoles and the variety Rosdom 204 was most tolerant to the sodium azide treatment.

Recommendation

In view of the results obtained from this study it can be recommended that low and moderate doses (2 and 4mM) of sodium azide should be employed to induce beneficial variability in groundnut thereby creating beneficial mutants which can be utilized in breeding programs to enhance yield and quality of this crop.

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